

Distribution Studies of some Metal Ions in Nitric Acid— Nonaqueous Mixtures on Quaternary Amine Styrene Butadiene Phenolformaldehyde

A. S. ABOUL-MAGD*, F. H. KAMAL, H. SHEHATA and E. A. HASSAN

Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Al-Azhar University, Nasr City, Cairo, Egypt

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Anion-exchange characteristics of Fe^{III} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} ions have been investigated in nitric acid solution as eluting agent with different proportions of organic solvents on a new anion-exchanger styrene butadiene phenolformaldehyde quaternary amine. The effect of concentration of organic solvents as well as acidity on the K_d values of these metal ions show the importance of such media as complexing agents. The possibilities of several successful separations have been carried out and based on the measurements of distribution results.

A number of complexing agents have been used for elution of some divalent ions in aqueous solution on anion-exchange resin column¹⁻³. Addition of polar organic solvents to water solutions modifies the affinities of sorption of metal ions, thus producing a condition that is widely different from that in the absence of solvent⁴. In addition, the distribution coefficient of metal ions increases with the increase in chain length of alcohol⁵. Ion-exchange distribution of tri- and di-valent metal ions has been investigated in aqueous nitric acid—methanol media with Dowex-1x4 exchanger, increasing the concentration of methanol leads to increased complex formation and changes in K_d values⁶. A description on the adsorption behaviour of some divalent metal ions towards strongly basic anion-exchanger in nitrite—methanolic solution and possible separation in such media was reported⁷.

The present work gives distribution coefficients of some divalent and trivalent metal ions measured in various combination of nitric acid, and organic solvents—water media using a quaternary amine styrene butadiene phenolformaldehyde exchanger. Some separation possibilities are also discussed on the basis of the distribution data.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were either of AnalaR or G.R. (E. Merk) grade.

Method of preparation: Strongly basic quaternary amine anion-exchanger was synthesised using the general method⁸ by the reaction of formalin (40%) with phenol in alkaline medium to prepare first the phenol—formaldehyde resin. Styrene—butadiene copolymer (10 g) dissolved in dichloroethane, phenol—formaldehyde (90 g) and concentrated HCl (2 ml) were thoroughly mixed and heated at 80° over a hot-

plate with continuous stirring. The paste obtained was washed several time with distilled water, dried and crushed.

The resin (50 g) was charged to a 3-necked flask followed by the addition of dichloroethane (200 g), paraformaldehyde (200 g) and anhydrous ZnCl_2 (40 g) as a catalyst. The reaction mixture was heated at 80° for 6–8 h under continuous stirring and HCl gas bubbling. Chloromethylation was repeated four times to reach the optimum degree of chloromethylation. The product was neutralised with saturated sodium carbonate solution and left overnight, then washed with distilled water till neutral washings were obtained (yield 52.6 g).

The chloromethylated product (50 g) was stirred with triethylamine (50 g) at 90° for 8 h. The process of amination was repeated four times. The product was filtered (54 g), immersed in saturated NaCl solution and washed finally with distilled water till pH of the wash-water was 2–3. The product was then regenerated with 0.5 N HNO_3 , washed with ethanol till neutral to methyl orange indicator. The resin was ground and screened to obtain different sizes using test sieves (ASTM-E 11-61).

As the determination of exchange capacity is simple with chloride form, the dry resin in chloride form (5 g) was used to determine the exchange capacity^{9,10} (0.9 mequiv./g dry resin).

The ir spectrum of styrene—butadiene rubber was compared with that of its crosslinked polymer with phenol—formaldehyde quaternary amine. A new peak was observed in the latter at 600–800 cm^{-1} due to the chloride group.

The stability of styrene—butadiene—phenol-formaldehyde quaternary amine was studied after treatment with several reagents. The change in the exchange capacity ranged from 2.0–5.5% as shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1—CHANGE IN VALUES OF CAPACITY OF STYRENE-BUTADIENE-PHENOLFORMALDEHYDE RESIN QUATERNARY AMINE (Cl⁻-FORM) AFTER TREATMENT WITH VARIOUS REAGENTS

Reagent used	Capacity of resin in mequiv./g dry resin
Blank (no reagent)	0.90
NaOH (1 N) for 48 h	0.85
HCl (1 N) for 48 h	0.90
H ₂ SO ₄ (0.5 N) for 48 h	0.88
HNO ₃ (0.5 N) for 48 h	0.88
Acetone, benzene, carbon tetrachloride, methanol, ethanol, DMSO, chloroform and dioxane for 48 h	0.90
Boiling water for 8 h	0.90
Thermal treatment in drying oven at 120° for 12 h	0.88

Preparation of the salt solution: The salt solutions were prepared from their nitrates to obtain exactly 0.1 N solution of Fe^{III}, Zn^{II}, Mg^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} in aqueous and aqueous organic solvent (40, 60 and 80%, v/v) media.

DMSO, isopropanol, ethanol, methanol, dioxane and acetone were used as solvents.

Determination of various elements: Most of the elements investigated were determined titrimetrically using suitable chelatometric method with EDTA-disodium salt as the titrant. The indicators used for these titrations were murexide, eriochrome black T and xylenol orange together in presence of suitable buffer solutions^{11,12}, dilute HNO₃ solution with hexamine for Cd^{II}¹³ and sulphosalicylic acid for Fe^{III}. Microgram quantities of the element were determined spectrophotometrically in case of separation procedure using Beckman B spectrophotometer with 1 cm cell.

Determination of K_d: The distribution study was carried out in a 100 ml glass-stoppered flask containing the dry resin (1 g) and 0.1 N metal ion solution (50 ml) in aqueous and aqueo-organic-HNO₃ media. Batches were equilibrated by shaking for 24 h. All the experiments were carried out at 25 ± 0.1°. Each solution was analysed for the metal ion⁸. The column separation procedure was the same as reported earlier⁴⁻⁶.

The values of distribution coefficient (K_d) were calculated using the relation⁸:

$$K_d = \frac{\text{mequiv. metal/g of dry resin}}{\text{mequiv. metal/ml of solution}}$$

Results and Discussion

Measurements of the adsorption behaviour of Fe^{III}, Zn^{II}, Mg^{II}, Cd^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} in various aquo-organic solvents at a constant overall acidity of 0.05 N HNO₃, are given in Table 2. The K_d values are zero for Zn, Mg, Cd, Co, Ni and Cu ions with change in DMSO concentration, whereas for Fe ion the K_d value was higher than one. Strong

solvating effect (such as DMSO) may cause the metal ions to remain mostly in the solution phase outside the resin. This behaviour is apparent with the divalent ions, which indicates the tendency of metal ion to form negatively charged nitrate complexes⁴. The data obtained indicates no significant advantage for the dimethyl sulphoxide over aqueous medium.

The influence of increasing proportion of isopropanol, ethanol, methanol, dioxane and acetone on the distribution coefficient values of metal ions are given in Tables 2-4. The K_d values increase with the increase in the concentration of organic solvents, showing that the addition of organic solvents to water medium in presence of 0.05 N HNO₃-0.5 N HNO₃, modifies the selectivities in a number of cases, excepting the ion of Co, Ni and Cu which were found the weakest adsorbed element⁶ and thus leading to separation possibilities which are otherwise unattainable in aqueous medium⁴⁻⁶. The K_d values of the elements are higher in 80% (v/v) of organic solvents than in mixture containing 40 or 60% (v/v) of the solvent under the same conditions of acidity. The K_d values for Fe^{III} in 60 and 80% (v/v) alcoholic nitric acid media could not be determined because of the formation of an insoluble compound on the resin. Whereas in dioxane or dioxane-nitric acid media highest K_d values were obtained.

TABLE 2—VARIATION OF DISTRIBUTION COEFFICIENTS OF SOME METALS WITH VARIATION OF ORGANIC SOLVENTS AT CONSTANT OVERALL ACIDITY OF 0.05 N HNO₃ IN PRESENCE OF STYRENE-BUTADIENE-PHENOL-FORMALDEHYDE ANION-EXCHANGER (NO₃⁻-FORM)

Solvent % (v/v)	K _d values						
	Fe ^{III}	Zn ^{II}	Mg ^{II}	Cd ^{II}	Co ^{II}	Ni ^{II}	Cu ^{II}
DMSO							
0.0	1.20	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
40	2.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
60	2.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
80	3.30	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Isopropanol							
40	10.0	9.80	2.00	2.50	0.00	0.00	0.00
60	ppt.	13.80	3.60	5.20	0.20	0.00	0.60
80	ppt.	30.00	8.50	9.70	0.30	0.00	0.80
Ethanol							
40	9.50	7.80	1.60	2.10	0.00	0.00	0.90
60	ppt.	12.00	2.50	3.90	0.00	0.00	0.00
80	ppt.	22.00	5.50	8.40	0.00	0.00	0.00
Methanol							
40	7.50	3.60	0.90	1.50	0.00	0.00	0.00
60	ppt.	8.50	1.40	3.20	0.00	0.00	0.00
80	ppt.	15.00	2.50	6.60	0.00	0.00	0.00
Dioxane							
40	25.00	12.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
60	68.00	16.00	0.00	7.90	0.50	0.20	0.40
80	92.00	37.00	9.77	7.90	0.60	0.50	0.50
Acetone							
40	13.50	10.00	3.50	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
60	45.00	12.00	5.80	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
80	78.00	22.00	7.50	5.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

TABLE 3—VARIATION OF DISTRIBUTION COEFFICIENTS OF SOME METALS WITH VARIATION OF ORGANIC SOLVENTS AT CONSTANT OVERALL ACIDITY OF 0.1 N HNO₃ IN PRESENCE OF STYRENE-BUTADIENE-PHENOL-FORMALDEHYDE ANION-EXCHANGER (NO₃⁻-FORM)

Solvent % (v/v)	Fe ^{III}	Zn ^{II}	Mg ^{II}	Cd ^{II}	Co ^{II}	Ni ^{II}	Cu ^{II}
	<i>K_d</i> values						
DMSO							
0.0	2.00	1.50	1.20	0.90	0.00	0.00	0.00
40	6.90	2.10	1.90	1.10	0.00	0.00	0.00
60	7.50	2.35	2.00	2.33	0.00	0.00	0.00
80	9.00	2.80	3.10	3.50	0.50	0.00	0.30
Isopropanol							
40	17.00	14.00	4.60	4.80	1.20	0.80	1.30
60	ppt.	22.50	6.80	5.00	2.90	1.50	1.70
80	ppt.	51.50	8.50	7.20	3.50	1.90	2.10
Ethanol							
40	15.00	8.50	3.50	3.00	1.00	0.00	0.00
60	ppt.	17.00	5.00	4.50	1.40	1.00	1.00
80	ppt.	45.00	6.50	5.00	2.20	1.50	1.50
Methanol							
40	11.50	4.00	2.50	2.20	0.00	0.00	0.00
60	ppt.	10.50	3.90	2.50	0.00	0.00	0.00
80	ppt.	30.00	5.50	3.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Dioxane							
40	45.00	14.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
60	87.00	20.00	0.00	9.50	2.80	3.70	5.50
80	108.50	51.00	24.00	15.00	3.80	4.50	6.50
Acetone							
40	22.00	10.00	0.00	0.50	0.00	0.00	0.00
60	76.00	21.00	0.00	0.50	0.00	0.00	0.00
80	97.00	35.00	16.00	7.50	2.30	5.00	3.50

TABLE 4—VARIATION OF DISTRIBUTION COEFFICIENTS OF SOME METALS WITH VARIATION OF ORGANIC SOLVENTS AT CONSTANT OVERALL ACIDITY OF 0.5 N HNO₃ IN PRESENCE OF STYRENE-BUTADIENE-PHENOL-FORMALDEHYDE ANION-EXCHANGER (NO₃⁻-FORM)

Solvent % (v/v)	Fe ^{III}	Zn ^{II}	Mg ^{II}	Cd ^{II}	Co ^{II}	Ni ^{II}	Cu ^{II}
	<i>K_d</i> values						
DMSO							
0.0	5.00	2.30	2.00	3.50	0.80	0.85	0.95
40	8.50	3.90	2.60	3.50	0.80	0.85	1.00
60	18.00	7.50	3.40	3.50	0.80	0.85	1.00
80	33.00	9.50	3.90	4.20	1.20	0.90	1.60
Isopropanol							
40	32.50	20.00	8.90	9.20	3.60	3.00	4.10
60	ppt.	35.00	15.00	11.00	5.80	3.00	4.00
80	ppt.	60.00	22.00	17.00	5.70	3.60	4.20
Ethanol							
40	25.00	18.00	5.00	6.00	2.50	1.50	2.30
60	ppt.	33.00	7.50	7.00	3.10	2.40	2.50
80	ppt.	45.00	7.80	7.50	4.30	3.00	3.00
Methanol							
40	21.00	15.00	3.00	3.00	1.90	0.00	0.00
60	ppt.	22.00	5.50	3.50	2.90	0.00	2.00
80	ppt.	64.00	5.50	4.20	3.70	2.50	3.00
Dioxane							
40	55.00	20.00	0.00	0.00	2.00	2.00	2.30
60	100.00	35.00	0.00	12.00	6.00	5.00	3.00
80	147.00	52.00	33.00	18.00	6.00	5.00	8.00
Acetone							
40	50.00	17.00	0.00	5.00	2.50	1.50	0.00
60	70.00	20.00	0.00	8.00	3.50	2.00	0.00
80	96.00	28.00	18.00	8.00	5.00	2.00	5.00

It is seen that the sorption of metal ions increases with a decrease in the dielectric constant (DC) of the individual, i.e. with growing chain length and molecular weight of the alcohol⁵. Investigations with respect to the effect of nitric acid concentration on the sorption of metal ions show that the sorption of metal ions increases gradually with increasing concentration of nitric acid (Tables 2–4). Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Mg^{II} ions are adsorbed more at 80% (v/v) of organic solvents with 0.5 N HNO₃ solution, whereas Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} ions are least adsorbed in 80% (v/v) organic solvents. Moreover, an increase in nitric acid concentration from 0.05 to 0.5 N HNO₃ considerably increases the distribution coefficients values; this change becomes more pronounced as the ability of the elements to form negatively charged ions increases (mainly negative nitrate complexes). Our results agree with those of John and Joseph⁶ who used methanol–10% HNO₃ mixture.

Comparison of the adsorption behaviour in organic solvents with the increase of acid concentration from 0.05 to 0.5 N HNO₃ shows considerable increases in the distribution coefficients values in the following order of total molarity of the solution, 0.05 N < 0.1 N < 0.5 N.

Separation of Fe^{III} and Cu^{II}: The synthesised styrene–butadiene–phenolformaldehyde quaternary amine resin was used in nitrate form. The prepared resin was packed in a glass column (1.2 cm dia. × 30 cm) and washed with 0.05 N HNO₃. Fe(NO₃)₃ solution (2 ml) was mixed with Cu(NO₃)₂ solution (2 ml) in 0.05 N HNO₃, and the mixture was passed through the column at a flow rate of 0.3 ml min⁻¹. A 0.05 N HNO₃ solution (120 ml) was passed through the column at the same flow rate. This quantitatively eluted copper. Fe^{III} ion was then eluted with 0.025 N HNO₃ solution (60 ml). The concentration of copper and iron were determined titrimetrically with EDTA–disodium salt. Fig. 1(a) shows the elution curve for the separation of Cu^{II} and Fe^{II}. The amount taken (recovered) for the two ions was Cu^{II}, 10 mg (9.12 mg); Fe^{III}, 10 mg (9.98 mg).

The observed *K_d* values (Tables 2–4) could be used to arrive at optimum conditions for the separation of different metal ions which are otherwise unattainable in aqueous medium. Thus at 0.05 N HNO₃–80%(v/v) acetone, it is possible to separate Fe^{III} from Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II}. The separation of Mg^{II} from Fe^{III} and Zn^{II} is also possible at 60%(v/v) dioxane or acetone–0.5 N HNO₃ media. Whereas Ni^{II} can be separated from all the studied metal ions using 60%(v/v) methanol–nitric acid (0.5 N).

Separation of Zn^{II} from Co and Cu in binary system: The same procedure was used for the separation of Zn^{II} and Cu^{II} Fig. 1(b). The prepared resin column was first washed with aqueous 40%(v/v) methanol solution–0.5 N HNO₃ (100 ml). Zn(NO₃)₂ solution (2 ml) was mixed with Cu(NO₃)₂ solution

Fig. 1. Elution curve for separation of (a) Cu^{II} and Fe^{III} , (b) Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} , and (c) Co^{II} and Zn^{II} using anion-exchanger (NO_3^- -form).

(2 ml) and passed at a flow rate 0.3 ml min^{-1} . The first elution solvent required to elute Cu^{II} was 0.5 N HNO_3 containing 80%(v/v) methanol. Zn^{II} was next eluted with 0.05 N HNO_3 . The amount taken (recovered) for the two ions was Cu^{II} , 10 mg(9.3 mg) ; Zn^{II} , 10 mg (10.0 mg).

The procedure is also valid for separation of zinc from cobalt except that the volume of solution Fig. 1(c). The amount taken (recovered) for the two ions was Co^{II} , 10 mg (9.96 mg) ; Zn^{II} , 10 mg (10.0 mg).

Fe^{II} was separated from Mg using the above procedure. The first elution solvent required to elute Mg^{II} was 0.5 N HNO_3 -40%(v/v) dioxane. Fe^{III} was then eluted with 0.025 N HNO_3 . The amount taken (recovered) for the two ions was Mg^{II} , 10 mg (9.2 mg) ; Fe^{III} 10.0 mg (9.89 mg) (Fig. 2a). Cd^{II} was next separated from Fe^{II} following the same procedure except that the first elution solvent was 0.05 N HNO_3 -40 or 60%(v/v) acetone which eluted Cd^{II} quantitatively. Fe^{III} was then eluted with 0.025 N HNO_3 with in 4 fraction of 20 ml. The

Fig. 2. Elution curve for separation of (a) Mg^{II} and Fe^{III} , and (b) Cd^{II} and Fe^{III} using anion-exchanger (NO_3^- -form).

amount taken (recovered) for the two ions was Cd^{II} , 10.0 mg (9.97 mg) ; Fe^{III} , 10 mg (9.98 mg) (Fig. 2b).

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